

APPLICATION OF INTERACTIVE TECHNIQUES IN ELEMENTARY ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Annotation: This article will focus on effective, modern and innovative methods of teaching English in order to increase my student's interest in language learning in primary classes. There will also be opinions and comments about the application of interactive techniques in elementary English lessons.

Keywords: mixed technique, interesting games, elementary classes, modern innovative techniques, pantomime.

After the independence of our country, the interest of young people in learning foreign languages has increased, and many opportunities for language learning are being created by our state. It is known that in order to further increase their interest in teaching English starting from the primary school year, to teach them foreign languages, starting from the 1st grade in all secondary schools, the teaching of English lessons in different forms of interesting games and at the same time the development of oral speech of students, starting from the 2nd grade,

Recently, the number of people at any age who learn English is growing very much. This is because in the process of life it is becoming more difficult to live without knowledge of English. But language learning also depends on age periods. Even scientists have proven that children absorb languages quickly and easily than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency to language learning in children, the fact that they have a strong imitation feature, the abundance of children's time compared to adults and the rapid storage of learned information.

Especially positive in primary education one of the decisions that led to the changes is the resolution of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 "on measures for further improvement of the Foreign Language Learning System" PP-1875 . According to this decision, in order to further increase their interest in teaching foreign languages, mainly English, starting from the primary school, teaching them foreign languages, starting from the 1st grade in all secondary schools, the teaching of English lessons in different ways of interesting games, and at the same time the development of oral speech by students, starting from the 2nd grade, Recently, the number of people at any age who learn English is growing very much. This is because in the process of life

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As one of the Chinese inventors Masaru Ibuka wrote in his famous book "very late after the real": "...the child's brain can have an unlimited amount of information..." Again, it should be noted that children aged 6-7 years do not understand the meaning of data, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, it is necessary not to start to an elementary school student who is also learning English. Otherwise, from the first step of teaching a foreign language, the child can get tired and slow down his interest in language learning. Because it is difficult to teach a foreign language to students in the primary class at the same time is one of the responsible tasks. For this reason, the following innovative techniques can be used to teach English to the elementary classes meaningful and interesting:

To be remembered by sight. It is known that young children remember their subjects, which they saw more often than they heard. Therefore, the lesson is taught by various visual weapons, posters, something visible and often used in everyday life, writing on objects, teaching new words and making sentences with the participation of new words learned. For example, writing to book (book), table (table), whiteboard (blackboard), Pen (pen), Window (window), etc. Such a thing, which is often used in everyday life-the child learns these words in an involuntary way, since the object is constantly falling into the eye and constantly applied.

Through songs and poems, to put words that is difficult to understand or Remember into music and sing. In addition to remembering new words in this, the verbal speech of the child develops. An example of this can be shown that the children's learning of the English alphabet by singing is more effective than simply memorizing.

Mixed technique here, we can combine different techniques on request. For example, in this can play children's games, sing songs, draw pictures, show new words through different actions. The advantage of the technique is in diversity. In this, the reader is not limited only by one thing.

Teach through cartoons. It is known that children are interested in seeing different cartoons. And in the process of seeing cartoons in English, the cartoon tries to understand the words that they are using through the actions of the heroes of the cartoon, although they do not understand what is said in the cartoon. And this is an interesting and effective way for children to learn a language.

Learning through fun games; the role of teaching through various games in teaching English science is incomparable. Playing various games during the lesson will further increase the enthusiasm for learning science in the classroom, motivating inactive students to participate better in the lessons as well. The following games can be an example of our word.

"Merry Riddles" (Merry Riddles) teaching puzzles to students is important in teaching English, they learn words that are unfamiliar to them, and they find the answer to thinking riddles.

"Pantomime" (pantomime). In this the teacher tells the reader any words, and the reader shows it. And the rest of the pupils will have to find the word and say the English name.

Learn through the sensory organs (to taste vegetables, fruits, food, to see, to hold different items, to smell flowers). Before studying this new method, it is necessary to cite the thoughts of a practicing psychologist: "a pedagogical child who wants something to be firmly fixed in the children's memory should try to make as many of the sensory organs as possible to harden his eyes, ears, sound organ, muscular senses and even, in the process of remembering the organs of smell

In fact, language learning through sensory organs is more useful and effective than other methods. For example, the reader in the process of tasting only one Apple knows what its color, taste, size, smell is and also says its English name. As a result, when the teacher asks the children for the English name of the colors, they immediately remember the time when the children ate the fruit. This means that the use of such methods will help the reader to keep the data in his memory in the long term.

In conclusion, it should be noted that teaching a language to primary school students is not an obligation, but rather an act of taking them with the use of interesting games and innovative techniques, which can serve as a foundation for the knowledge they will receive in the future. Therefore, as the education system sets itself the task of nurturing a free-thinking, harmonious, mature personality, in the future, we will be able to make our own contribution with the further development of ways of effective use of innovative technologies by future teachers.

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